

ANALYSIS OF THE PRACTICE OF ESTABLISHING DIGITAL BANKS AND THEIR BRANCHES IN UZBEKISTAN

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Currently, the banking system of Uzbekistan, like other sectors, is undergoing large-scale transformation processes. These transformation processes are aimed at increasing the quality of services and ensuring their popularity through the wide introduction of advanced information technology achievements in traditional banking practices.

In particular, after the signing of the President's decision "On the measures to fundamentally improve the activities of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan", the banking system will have to establish "digital" banks and banking units specializing in retail banking and customer service. innovative banking technologies to further improve service quality.

Accordingly, in 2020, Anorbank and TBC Bank were registered as digital banks in Uzbekistan.

In fact, during 2015-2020, the concept of "digital banking" developed rapidly in European countries. Digital banks are making extensive use of modern digital innovations to provide more convenient and useful services to their customers.

Today, Anorbank and TBC Bank, both digital banks, offer their customers a full range of digital services via mobile applications or PCs. This means that a digital bank customer can access banking services 24/7. That is, in the digital banking system, a mobile application is presented to the client, and high flexibility

of banking operations is provided with a high-tech IT infrastructure based on the mobile application.

Of course, the question arises, what is the difference between today's commercial banks and newly established digital banks?

Digital banks tend to:

- not expanding the network of bank branches;
- 100% online communication system between the bank and the client;
- high-quality and convenient mobile application;
- the most favorable conditions for deposits and loans that meet market requirements (that is, based on consumer demand);
- availability of fast, high-quality, convenient and round-the-clock response centers;

For private or public banks, it is usual:

- insufficient attention is paid to the presence and quality of Bank branches in each district, city and region;
- low level of online communication between the bank and the client;
- mobile applications are created for appearance and the user logs in once and decides not to log in again (in mobile applications there are constant problems in the process of transferring money from card to card or paying utility bills, in most cases there are interruptions in the system circumstances);
- deposits and loans that meet market requirements are given, but in most cases only acquaintances play a big role (if there are no acquaintances, the client will wait for 3 months or more).
- fast, high-quality, convenient and round-the-clock answering centers work very poorly, while the client has to talk to specialists from all departments of the bank to get an answer to his question. The customer's time, the amount paid by the customer for telephone service is not taken into account.

This digital transformation of financial services will help to expand the economic opportunities of customers, while also creating a wide range of opportunities for bank customers, which is an important step towards increasing

financial activity. In other words, one of the prospects of digital banks is to reduce the cost of services by 40-60 percent due to the digitization of financial sectors. Visiting the bank saves customers time and money on paperwork.

The services provided through mobile payment systems mainly consist of transferring payments for the services of mobile operators, internet providers (through non-bank retail payment systems). The weight of transferring utility payments, taxes and other mandatory payments through the Clearing system is increasing.

Remote banking services are provided in the segment of legal entities and private entities, as well as individuals. The share of TIF National Bank, Agrobank, People's Bank, Ipoteka-bank and Sanoatkurilishbank in the total number of Mazur system users is incomparable, and their combined share is almost 50 percent.

Analyzing the users in separate segments, the largest share of legal entities and individuals corresponds to the contribution of Agrobank.

www.bankers.uz as a result of the research carried out by the site, a ranking of mobile applications created for providing remote services to individuals provided by commercial banks was compiled (Table 2).

Table 1

Rating of mobile applications of commercial banks created for remote services to individuals¹

No	Program name	Name of the bank	Number of downloads	The number of people who rated it on the Play Market	Average rating
1.	National	National Bank	500,000+	10352	3.9
2.	Partner Mobile	Partner bank	100,000+	2 733	3.7
3.	InfinBank	Infinbank	100,000+	2 249	3.9
4.	Ipal Road	Silk Road Bank	100,000+	1 881	4.0

¹Information from www.bankers.uz website

No	Program name	Name of the bank	Number of downloads	The number of people who rated it on the Play Market	Average rating
	Mobile				
5.	Mortgage Bank	Mortgage bank	100,000+	1 645	4.5
6.	Agrobank Mobile New	Agrobank	100,000+	1 523	3.8
7.	Uz PSB Mobile	Industrial Construction Bank	100,000+	1 415	3.6
8.	Orange	Kapitalbank	50,000+	4 722	4.6
9.	Contact Mobile	Aloqabank	50,000+	1 126	3.9
10.	MKB Mobile	Microcredit bank	50,000+	470	3.3
11.	Asaka Mobile	Asaka Bank	50,000+	266	3.2
12.	MyAlliance	Asian Alliance Bank	10,000+	564	3.6
13.	MyTuron	Turonbank	10,000+	399	4.4
14.	OFB24	Orient Finance Bank	10,000+	397	2.6
15.	QQB Mobile	Rural Construction Bank	10,000+	300	3.3
16.	Folk Mobile	People's Bank	10,000+	159	3.0
17.	TrustPay	Trustbank	10,000+	111	2.6
18.	RBK-Mobile	Ravnakbank	5000+	115	4.5
19.	Merchant Mobile	Savdogarbank	5000+	54	2.5
20.	DAVRBANK	Current bank	5000+	37	3.0
21.	UNO	Hi Tech Bank	1000+	87	3.6
22.	MultiPay KDB	KDB Bank Uzbekistan	1000+	63	3.3
23.	Turkestan Bank	Turkestanbank	1000+	41	3.6
24.	UniversalPay	Universalbank	1000+	30	3.0
25.	ZiraatBank Uzbekistan	ZiraatBank Uzbekistan	1000+	9	3.1
26.	Madad Invest Bnak Mobile	Madad Invest Bank	100+	6	3.0
27.	Capital Mobile	Poytakhtbank	10+	0	0.0

No	Program name	Name of the bank	Number of downloads	The number of people who rated it on the Play Market	Average rating
28.	In place	Industrial Construction Bank	100,000+	-	4
29.	Pomegranate	Anorbank	-	-	-
30.	Tenge	UzAgroExportbank	-	-	-
31.	TB	Tenge Bank			

It can be seen from the table that there are 7 banks with more than 100,000 downloads of mobile applications through the Play Market — InFinBank, Hamkorbank, Uzmilliybank, Agrobank, Ipoteka Bank, Silk Road Bank and UzSQB's mobile applications are organized. It should also be mentioned that the Asakabank mobile application is among the applications with more than 50,000 downloads.

A total of 23,900 people rated the mobile applications of 27 banks available on Play Market.

The most rated mobile applications through Play Market are "Apelsin" (Kapitalbank), "Milliy" (UzMilliybank), "Hamkor Mobile" (Hamkor Bank), "InfinBank" (Infinbank) and "Ipak Yo'li Mobile". (Silk Road Bank). Among these programs, Kapitalbank's "Apelsin" application (4.6 points) received the highest rating. It is worth noting that this program has been evaluated by a total of 4722 users through the Play Market.

At this point, it should be noted that Ipoteka bank mobile applications were evaluated by 1645 users, and the average score was 4.5 points.

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